

Spectrophotometric Studies on Complexes of Pd (II) and U (VI) with *p*-Phenylazosalicylaldehyde and *p*-Sodium Sulphophenylazosalicylaldehyde

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Two chelating agents namely, *p*-phenylazosalicylaldehyde (PAS), and *p*-Sodium Sulphophenylazosalicylaldehyde (SPAS) were synthesised and their chelating tendency with Pd(II) and U(VI) have been studied spectrally. The metal-ligand ratio in all the cases was found to be 1 : 2. The stability constants were calculated and the log K and the standard free energy of formation (ΔF) values of Pd(II) and U(VI)—*p*-phenylazosalicylaldehyde and U(VI) and Pd(II)—*p*-Sodium Sulphophenylazosalicylaldehyde chelates were found to be 7.64, 7.40, 7.13 and 7.22 and -10.6613 , -10.3200 , -9.9490 and -10.08 k.cals/mole respectively.

Salicylaldehyde forms metal chelates with a number of metal ions. Salicylaldehyde complexes of several divalent metal ions have been studied by Maley and Mellor¹. Calvin and Wilson² have investigated the effects of substitution of various groups in α -hydroxyaldehydes by studying their complexes. Vartak and Menon³ have studied various metal chelates of 2,4-dihydroxy- and 2,5-dihydroxybenzaldehydes. In the present investigation the metal complexes of phenyl substituted *p*-azo-salicylaldehyde have been studied by employing spectrophotometric technique.

EXPERIMENTAL

All the reagents were of A.R. grade.

Synthesis of the ligands :

(I) *p*-Phenylazosalicylaldehyde (PAS)

5 gms (3.9 ml) of aniline was dissolved in 28 ml of 6 *M* hydrochloric acid in a conical flask. The temperature of the flask and solution was maintained below 5° by immersion in an ice bath. The aniline solution was diazotised by the addition of 4 g of sodium nitrite in 19 ml of water while the temperature was not allowed to rise above 10°.

Completion of the reaction was tested with potassium iodide-starch paper. To this solution 5 gms of salicylaldehyde in 40 ml of 2*N* sodium hydroxide solution was added carefully, with continuous stirring. The precipitate thus formed was filtered, washed with water, recrystallised from alcohol and dried. The yield was approximately 85%.

The compound is brown coloured crystalline solid with melting point 107°–110°.

(II) *Synthesis of p*-Sodium Sulphophenylazosalicylaldehyde (SPAS)

The procedure is same except that instead of aniline sulfanilic acid was taken.

It is a bright red crystalline compound soluble in water.

The composition and structure of the compounds were established by elemental analysis and I.R. spectra. The structural formulae may be presented as follows :—

The instruments used were a Bausch and Lomb Spectronic-20 spectrophotometer and a Hilger & Watts spectrophotometer.

The studies of Pd(II) and U(VI) PAS chelates were carried out in 50% (v/v) alcohol water mixture at 30° while SPAS studies were carried out in aqueous medium.

Nature of the Complex

The λ_{\max} of the PAS was found at 430 nm while in the complex there was a Bathochromic shift from this wavelength to 500 nm (at pH—5.1) and 480 nm (at pH—4.0) for Pd(II) and U(VI) respectively and of SPAS was found at 590 nm and U(VI) and Pd(II) complexes at 630 nm and 390 nm (at pH—7.0). Hence these wave-lengths were chosen to study stoichiometry of the components by Job's continuous variation⁴, mole ratio⁵ and slope ratio⁶ methods. All the three methods gave a stoichiometry of metal to ligand as 1 : 2. The validity of Beer's law was seen. The absorbance measurements were carried out after 24 hrs equilibration. The colour did not fade even after one week revealing the stability of the chelates.

The apparent stability constants were calculated from the absorbance data using the mole ratio method.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Pd(II) and U(VI) were found to form 1 : 2 (M : L) complexes in all the cases. The log K values for the Pd(II) and U(VI) PAS and Pd(II) and U(VI)—SPAS chelates were calculated to be 7.64, 7.40, 7.22 and 7.13 respectively. The ΔF values for these complexes were found to be -10.6613, -10.3200, -10.080 and -9.9490 K.cals/mole respectively.

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